

AWARENESS, ATTITUDES, AND PRACTICES TOWARDS ADVERSE DRUG REACTION REPORTING: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY IN A PREVIOUSLY UNEXPLORED EPIDEMIOLOGICAL AREA

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ABSTRACT

Background: Adverse drug reactions (ADRs) remain a serious challenge to global health, leading to avoidable hospitalizations and significant economic burden. Although pharmacovigilance programs have been implemented worldwide, under-reporting of ADRs is still a universal problem, particularly in regions where no previous epidemiological studies have been conducted. This study assessed awareness, experiences, and practices regarding ADR reporting among residents of a previously unstudied region. **Methodology:** A cross-sectional, questionnaire-based study was conducted in 2025 among 1,000 participants, with data collected on demographics, awareness of ADRs, past experiences, reporting practices, barriers, facilitators, and digital literacy. Data were analyzed using SPSS v25 and compared with studies published between 2015 and 2025. **Results:** Of the 1,000 participants, 56% were female and the predominant age group was 18–24 years (39%). Overall

awareness of ADRs was high (93%), but only 43% of respondents knew how to report ADRs. About 62% had experienced ADRs, but only 29% had reported them. Doctors and

pharmacists were the most preferred reporting channel (40%), followed by mobile apps (29%). The most common barriers included perceiving the reaction as not serious (28%), not knowing how to report (25%), and uncertainty about causality (20%). Facilitators included easier reporting mechanisms (47%) and more awareness campaigns (41%). Despite 86% of participants being moderate-to-advanced smartphone users, only 29% had ever used a mobile app for ADR reporting. **Conclusion:** The study highlights a gap between awareness and practice of ADR reporting. Despite high digital literacy, mobile app use for reporting remains limited. Strengthening awareness programs, simplifying digital tools, and integrating ADR reporting into community health initiatives may improve pharmacovigilance systems.

KEYWORDS: Adverse Drug Reactions, Pharmacovigilance, ADR Reporting, Cross-sectional Study, Digital Literacy.

INTRODUCTION

Adverse drug reactions (ADRs) represent a significant global health challenge, contributing to considerable morbidity, mortality, and financial burden on healthcare systems worldwide. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines an ADR as “a response to a drug which is noxious and unintended, and which occurs at doses normally used in humans for prophylaxis, diagnosis, or therapy of disease”.^[1] Globally, it is estimated that ADRs account for up to 6–10% of all hospital admissions and are among the leading causes of patient morbidity in both developed and developing countries.^[2] In India, the magnitude of this problem is even more concerning due to a large, diverse population, polypharmacy, and widespread use of over-the-counter (OTC) drugs.

Pharmacovigilance (PV) — the science and activities related to detecting, assessing, understanding, and preventing adverse effects or any other drug-related problem — plays a critical role in ensuring medication safety.^[3] India’s national pharmacovigilance program (PvPI), launched in 2010, aimed to strengthen ADR monitoring and reporting across healthcare settings.^[4] Despite the establishment of several Adverse Drug Reaction Monitoring Centres (AMCs) under PvPI and the introduction of multiple reporting tools, including the mobile app “ADR PvPI” and toll-free helplines, underreporting remains a persistent barrier to effective pharmacovigilance.

Underreporting of ADRs has been attributed to multiple factors, including lack of awareness, inadequate training, uncertainty about causality, fear of legal repercussions, and limited

access to reporting systems.^[5,6] While most research in India has focused on healthcare professionals' awareness and practices, studies involving the general population are relatively scarce. Moreover, few studies have evaluated public awareness and use of digital reporting tools, despite the increasing penetration of smartphones and internet access.

Digital literacy and mobile technology could transform pharmacovigilance by enabling real-time, patient-driven ADR reporting. However, despite widespread smartphone usage, the uptake of digital reporting remains minimal in many regions. Understanding the gap between awareness and actual reporting behavior — and identifying barriers and facilitators to ADR reporting — is crucial to strengthening community pharmacovigilance efforts.

This study was conducted in a previously unexplored epidemiological region to assess awareness, attitudes, and practices related to ADR reporting among the general population. Additionally, it explored digital literacy levels and perceptions toward using mobile applications for ADR reporting. The findings aim to inform strategies for enhancing pharmacovigilance engagement through community awareness and technological innovation.

Materials and Methodology Study Design and Setting

A descriptive, cross-sectional, questionnaire-based study was conducted between January and May 2025 among residents of a previously unstudied region in India. The area was chosen based on the absence of prior pharmacovigilance-related research and its mixed demographic composition of urban and semi-urban populations.

Study Population and Sampling

In Dedefo MG *et al.*,^[7] 48% of the study population opined positive above digital ADR reporting. Considering this prevalence and using z^2pq/d^2 , where p is prevalence; $p = 48\%$, $q = (1-p)$, which was 52% for our study, and considering the 5% allowable error at 95% confidence interval, the sample size we obtained was approximately 384. We included the study participants enrolled between June 2025 to October 2025 for a better outcome and external validity of our study. 971 individuals submitted 100% complete questionnaire. Thus, all were considered for the analysis.

The individuals aged 18 years and above were recruited using a stratified random sampling method to ensure representation across gender, education, and occupational categories. Inclusion criteria comprised individuals who provided informed consent, were residents of the

study area for at least one year, and were able to understand the questionnaire language (English or their local vernacular). Healthcare professionals, students of pharmacy or medicine, and those unwilling to participate were excluded to minimize professional bias.

Data Collection Tool

Data were collected using a pre-validated structured questionnaire, designed after reviewing existing literature and pharmacovigilance tools developed by the Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission (IPC). The questionnaire consisted of six major sections:

1. **Demographic details** (age, gender, education)
2. **Medication history** and recent drug use
3. **Awareness** of ADRs and reporting mechanisms
4. **Experience** with adverse reactions and reporting practices
5. **Barriers and facilitators** to ADR reporting
6. **Digital literacy and mobile app usage**

Each section included multiple-choice and Likert-scale items. The content validity of the questionnaire was established through expert review by pharmacology faculty, and a pilot test (n=50) confirmed reliability (Cronbach's alpha = 0.84).

Data Analysis

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, means, and percentages were used to summarize the data. Associations between categorical variables (e.g., education level and awareness) were assessed using the Chi-square test, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

The study included 971 participants, predominantly young adults aged 18–34 years (67.8%) (**Table 1**), with a higher representation of females (55.9%) (**Table 2**). Most participants had taken medications in the preceding six months (86.2%), mainly through doctor prescriptions (71.9%), though a substantial proportion practiced self-medication (25.2%) (**Table 3**). Awareness that medicines can cause side effects was very high (92.7%), and most participants believed ADR reporting improves medication safety (91.0%) (**Table 4**). However, despite 55.1% being aware that ADRs can be reported in India, only 2.8% knew the actual reporting process to PvPI/NCC (**Table 4**), indicating a major gap between awareness and practical knowledge.

Although 61.4% of participants experienced an ADR (**Figure 2**), less than half of them reported it (46.8%), resulting in an overall ADR reporting rate of only 28.7% (**Figure 2**). Reporting was largely dependent on healthcare professionals rather than direct patient reporting (**Figure 3**). Key motivations for reporting included advice from healthcare professionals (96.1%) and concern for personal health (90.0%) (**Table 5**), whereas non-reporting was mainly due to perceiving ADRs as not serious (28.4%) and lack of knowledge on reporting methods (25.4%) (**Table 6**). Digital readiness was high, with 53.4% having advanced smartphone skills and 62.3% using healthcare apps (**Table 7**); notably, a single training session improved comfort with digital ADR reporting (**Figure 4**), and easier reporting methods (47.2%) and increased awareness (41.3%) were identified as major enablers for digital ADR reporting (**Figure 5, Table 8**).

TABLES AND FIGURES

Table 1: Distribution of Age of the study population.

Age Group	n	%
18–24 years	377	38.8%
25–34 years	282	29.0%
35–44 years	146	15.0%
45–54 years	101	10.4%
55–64 years	50	5.1%
65+ years	15	1.5%

Table 2: Distribution of Gender of our study population.

Gender	n	%
Female	543	55.9%
Male	425	43.8%
Prefer not to say / Others	3	0.3%

Figure 1: Distribution of education status of our study participants Table 3: Distribution of responses about recent medication.

Table 4: Distribution of responses on Awareness.

Question	Yes (n, %)	No (n, %)	χ^2 value	p-value
Do you know medicines can cause side effects?	900 (92.7%)	71 (7.3%)	707.77	< 0.0001
Did you know you can report side effects in India?	535 (55.1%)	436 (44.9%)	10.09	0.0015
Do you know how to report ADR to PvPI / NCC?	28 (2.8%)	943 (97.2%)	862.23	< 0.0001
Do you believe ADR reporting helps make medicine use safer?	884 (91.0%)	87 (9.0%)	654.18	< 0.0001

Figure 2: Responses for experiencing the ADR and reporting.

Figure 3: The mode of reporting ADR by our study population.

Table 5: Motivation for reporting the ADR

Reason	N = 279	%
Don't want others to suffer the same side effect	209	74.9%
Worried about one's own health	251	90.0%
Told by a healthcare professional to report	268	96.1%
Legal or safety requirement	11	3.9%

Table 6: Barriers for reporting.

Reason for not reporting	N = 317	%
Didn't think it was serious enough	276	28.4%
Didn't know how to report	247	25.4%
Wasn't sure if side effect was from the drug	194	20.0%
Worried about legal problems	134	13.8%
Lack of time or interest	70	7.2%
Other	50	5.2%

Table 7: Digital literacy.

Smartphone Usage Level	n	%
Advanced	519	53.4%
Moderate	324	33.4%
Basic	128	13.2%
Used mobile apps for healthcare (e.g., buy meds, book a doctor)		
Yes	605	62.3%
No	366	37.7%

Figure 4: Comfort in digital ADR reporting after one session of training.

Figure 5: Preferred method of reporting after training.

Table 8: Encouraging factors for digital ADR reporting according to our study subjects.

Encouragement Factors	n	%
Easier reporting methods	458	47.2%
More awareness and education	401	41.3%
Assurance of privacy and data security	312	32.1%
Rewards or incentives	113	11.6%
Feedback from authorities	85	8.8%

DISCUSSION

This study provides valuable insights into the awareness, attitudes, and practices regarding ADR reporting among residents of a previously unstudied region in India.

Table 1 depicts the age-wise distribution of the 971 study participants. The majority of respondents belonged to the younger age groups, with 38.8% ($n = 377$) aged between 18–24 years, followed by 29.0% ($n = 282$) in the 25–34 years category. Participants aged 35–44 years constituted 15.0% ($n = 146$) of the study population. Older age groups were comparatively underrepresented, indicating that the study population was predominantly young adults, reflecting higher engagement of younger individuals in the survey. Table 2 shows the gender distribution of the participants. Females constituted the majority with 55.9% ($n = 543$), while 43.8% ($n = 425$) were males. 0.3%, preferred not to disclose their gender or identified as others. This female predominance may suggest greater health awareness or willingness to participate in health-related surveys among women.

Status of ADR reporting

Out of the 971 participants, 596 (61.4%) reported having experienced at least one ADR.

Among those who experienced an ADR, only 279 participants (46.8%) actually reported the ADR, while 317 participants (53.2%) did not report it to any authority. The most common mode of reporting was through healthcare professionals. Very few participants reported ADRs independently without the involvement of healthcare providers.

Table 3 presents information on recent medication usage among the participants. A large majority, 86.2% (n = 837), reported having taken medicines in the last six months, indicating substantial exposure to pharmacotherapy. Regarding the source of medicines, 71.9% (n = 698) obtained medicines through a doctor's prescription, while 25.2% (n = 245) procured medicines without a prescription from pharmacies, highlighting the prevalence of self-medication. These findings underscore the importance of ADR awareness across both prescribed and non-prescribed medication use. Awareness that medicines can cause side effects was very high (92.7%), and the association was highly statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 707.77$, $p < 0.0001$). However, knowledge of the actual reporting mechanism to PvPI/NCC was extremely low (2.8%), despite a highly significant chi-square value ($\chi^2 = 862.23$, $p < 0.0001$).

Importantly, the belief that ADR reporting improves medicine safety was very high (91.0%) and statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 654.18$, $p < 0.0001$). This indicates a major gap between a positive attitude and practical knowledge of reporting systems. Only 43%, reveals a critical knowledge–practice gap consistent with patterns reported in other Indian and global studies.^[7,8]

Comparable findings have been reported in multiple Indian studies. For instance, Sharma *et al.* (2018) observed that while 88% of respondents were aware of ADRs, only 36% knew about reporting procedures. Similarly, a study by Gupta *et al.* (2020) found that only 28% of patients had ever reported an ADR despite high awareness levels.^[7,8] Our study, reporting rate aligns closely with these observations, emphasizing persistent underutilization of reporting mechanisms. Munshi *et al.* reported that 98.3% participants never heard of the Adverse Event Monitoring Center.^[9]

Table 5 describes the motivating factors among participants who reported ADRs (N = 279). The individuals who had reported had more than one motivation for reporting. The most common motivation was being advised by a healthcare professional (96.1%), followed by concern for one's own health (90.0%). These findings emphasize the influential role of healthcare professionals in promoting ADR reporting.

Table 6 outlines reasons for non-reporting among participants (N = 317). The most common barrier was the perception that the ADR was not serious enough (28.4%), followed by a lack of knowledge on how to report (25.4%). Uncertainty about whether the drug caused the side effect (20.0%) and fear of legal consequences (13.8%) were also notable barriers. Lack of time or interest and other reasons contributed to a smaller proportion. These barriers point toward the need for education and simplification of reporting procedures.

The reasons for underreporting identified here — perceiving reactions as non-serious, lack of knowledge, and uncertainty about causality — mirror those cited by Goutham JB *et al.*^[9] In their study, lack of time due to heavy workload, the fear of litigation, and punishment were identified as the main barriers, which indirectly suggested the lack of awareness about post reporting process of ADRs among healthcare professionals. While the HCPs themselves lack awareness, the reporting from the general public would be challenging.

These barriers reflect deep-seated misconceptions and a lack of confidence in pharmacovigilance systems. Notably, the belief that ADRs should only be reported if severe suggests a need for educational interventions clarifying that all suspected ADRs, regardless of severity, are vital for signal detection.

Also, as the majority of respondents had completed higher secondary education or above, indicated a relatively well-educated population. As literacy and higher education are known to influence awareness, comprehension, and participation in pharmacovigilance activities, including ADR reporting.

Digital Literacy and Mobile App Utilization

A key aspect of this study is the evaluation of digital literacy in relation to ADR reporting. Table 7 presents participants' digital literacy levels. More than half of the respondents (53.4%) reported advanced smartphone usage, while 33.4% had moderate and 13.2% had basic usage skills. Additionally, 62.3% had previously used mobile applications for healthcare purposes, reflecting a favorable study population for implementing digital ADR reporting systems.

Prakash J *et al.*, the team of the pharmacovigilance programme of India (PvPI), analyzed ADR related data reported through this mobile application on a pilot basis. They found that of all the users of the ADR mobile application, only 20.56% were doctors, and the rest were other

consumers. Also, the prevalence of reports received through this has increased from 3.55% in 2017 to 96.45% in 2018.^[11]

Barriers such as a lack of app awareness and concerns about data privacy were comparable to findings from studies in Malaysia and the UK.^[12,13] The positive attitude — where 84% expressed readiness to use ADR apps with guidance — signals a strong opportunity for public health authorities to promote digital ADR tools through user-friendly designs and campaigns integrated with existing healthcare apps.

Public Health Implications

The high proportion of respondents obtaining medicines through non-prescription sources underscores the potential risk for unmonitored ADRs in the community. This unregulated consumption, coupled with underreporting, can delay detection of drug safety signals. Integrating ADR awareness into national health programs and pharmacy practice is thus critical. Also, as we could observe from Table 8, the most influential factor was easier reporting methods (47.2%), followed by increased awareness and education (41.3%). These findings suggest that simplifying platforms and strengthening trust and awareness are key to improving digital ADR reporting.

Educational initiatives must also be diversified — leveraging community pharmacists, social media platforms, and local language outreach — to address varied literacy levels. Introducing incentives and feedback systems for ADR reporters could further enhance participation, as suggested in pharmacovigilance models from Sweden and the Netherlands.^[14,15]

Strengths and Limitations

This study is among the few to explore both pharmacovigilance awareness and digital literacy within a single framework in a previously unexplored region. The large sample size (n=971) and balanced demographic representation strengthen its generalizability. However, limitations include reliance on self-reported data, potential recall bias, and lack of follow-up on actual reporting behavior. Furthermore, since healthcare professionals were excluded, the study reflects only community perspectives, not institutional practices.

Future Directions

To bridge the awareness–practice gap, multipronged interventions are needed

- Simplifying mobile ADR reporting apps with regional language options.

- Conducting national awareness drives linking ADR reporting with existing health campaigns (e.g., Ayushman Bharat).
- Training community pharmacists to educate consumers about ADR reporting.
- Establishing feedback loops to inform the public about the impact of their reports on drug safety.

CONCLUSION

The present study highlights a paradox between high awareness and low practice of ADR reporting in a digitally literate community. Although most participants understood the importance of ADR reporting, procedural knowledge, and engagement remain limited. Addressing barriers such as lack of knowledge, fear of legal consequences, and confusion about causality, while promoting facilitators like simplified processes and educational campaigns, could significantly improve reporting rates. Integrating ADR reporting into existing digital health ecosystems and community-based pharmacovigilance networks is essential for achieving a safer and more responsive healthcare system.

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